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Final Defense of a Dissertation on

Utilization of National Guard Cyber Forces in Title 32 Status for National Cyber Missions

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The overall classification of this brief is

UNCLASSIFIED

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 - Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP)

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Acknowledgments (cont)

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About Me

Civilian

- Director, National Security Initiatives, University of Wisconsin–Madison
- Research Director, Wisconsin Security Research Consortium

Academic

- PhD Candidate, Cyber Defense, Dakota State University
- MS, Cybersecurity Policy, University of Maryland Global Campus
- MA, Intelligence Studies (Information Warfare), American Military University
- BA, Intelligence Studies (Information Operations), American Military University
- Space Systems Certificate (SSC), Naval Postgraduate School
- Joint Professional Military Education (JPME), Naval War College

Military

- Army National Guard Cyber Warfare Officer (17A), Signal Officer (25A), and Military Intelligence Officer (35A), assigned to 176th Cyber Protection Team (CPT)
- Prior Navy Reserve Cryptologic Warfare Officer (1815) and Space Cadre
- Broad experience with Guard and Reserve Component (RC) cyber matters
- Experience planning, executing, and directing Cyberspace Operations (CO)

Cybersecurity is National Security

The Guard and Reserve Total Force is...

“a crucial part of achieving our mission of protecting the Nation in cyberspace.

Cybersecurity is national security. Malicious actors utilizing tools less than a few thousand dollars in value are capable of impacting national security. That's where the Total Force comes in, in terms of what we need to do collective as a team to protect national interest in cyberspace.” – 31 August 2021

“Protecting the nation against malicious cyber activity is a whole-of-nation effort involving partners from industry, academia, interagency, and the Guard and Reserve.” – 19 April 2022

— GEN Paul Nakasone; Director, National Security Agency; Chief, Central Security Service; Commander, U.S. Cyber Command, 2018–2024

Cyber Warfare is our Reality

“Cyber warfare is not just our future — **it is our contemporary reality.** The National Guard is positioned to be leaders in the digital domain, and continues to enhance our nation's cyber capabilities in combat and in the homeland. With 4,000 National Guard cyber operators across 40 states, many working for leading tech companies, the National Guard has the knowledge, skills, and abilities to play a critical role in the DoD's cyber enterprise.”

— GEN Daniel Hokanson, 19 April 2022;
Chief, National Guard Bureau, 2020–2024

We Need Cyber Total Force Integration

“USCYBERCOM is exploring innovative ways to **enhance our operations using the expertise resident in the National Guard and Reserves**. We operate side-by-side daily with activated members of the Reserve Component integrated into our teams, and we engage National Guard units on State Active Duty and State Partnership Program engagements.”

— Gen. Timothy D. Haugh, 12 April 2024; Director, National Security Agency; Chief, Central Security Service; Commander, U.S. Cyber Command, 2024–2025

We Need Cyber Total Force Integration

And again 1 year later, in April 2025:

“USCYBERCOM is exploring innovative ways to **enhance our operations using the expertise resident in the National Guard and Reserves**. We operate side-by-side daily with activated members of the Reserve Component integrated into our teams, and we engage National Guard units on State Active Duty and State Partnership Program engagements.”

— LTG Joe Hartman, 9 April 2025;
Performing the Duties of Director, National Security Agency; Chief, Central Security Service; Acting Commander, U.S. Cyber Command, 2025–2026

Cyber Innovation Must Be Our Way of Life

“Innovation is not just an option for the National Guard — it must be our way of life. [...] We must empower every Guardsman to think creatively, to experiment, and to fail forward. **It’s about fostering a culture where a cyber specialist in a small town can spark the next breakthrough that will ripple across the entire DoD.** We have something our adversaries cannot replicate: The ingenuity of the American spirit, embodied in the warrior ethos of our Citizen-Soldiers and Citizen-Airmen. [...] When we innovate, we decisively win.”

— Gen. Steve Nordhaus, Chief, National Guard Bureau, 18 March 2025

National Guard Cyber is on the Front Lines

“The National Guard provides critical cybersecurity and information technology support, including mission assurance, network assessment and protection and risk mitigation. [...] Many National Guard servicemembers hold cyber positions in their civilian jobs, allowing them to combine an intimate knowledge of leading-edge cyber technologies from the private sector with a deep appreciation of cyber tradecraft that comes from high-level security clearances and years of military training. The Guard’s cyber force is proud to fight on the frontlines of the cyber domain.”

— Gen. Steve Nordhaus, Chief, National Guard Bureau, 20 May 2025

National Guard Cyber is on the Front Lines

“Members of the National Guard enhance USCYBERCOM's missions and provide essential cyber capabilities to their home states. Many Guard members bring valuable private-sector experience, allowing them to quickly share threat information with state and local authorities. They can operate under Title 32 to protect critical infrastructure or be federally mobilized under Title 10 to directly support USCYBERCOM's national mission.”

— Lt. Gen. Joshua Rudd, 15 Jan 2026;
nominee for Director, National Security Agency;
Chief, Central Security Service;
Commander, U.S. Cyber Command

Study Rationale

- Recruiting and retention of military cyber experts in the reserve force
 - Engage personnel in meaningful work while meeting training requirements
- Meet clearly stated goals and intent for utilization of Guard Cyber expertise articulated by leaders across the military cyber enterprise and across the Guard and Reserve Cyber Forces
 - Engage the Guard and effectively align with national cyber mission needs

Research Questions

- 1** What elements of current law and policy support or constrain the utilization of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for federal cyber missions?
- 2** What precedent, expert opinion, and policy analysis enable or challenge the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for federal cyber missions?

Research Objectives

To address the identified policy gaps and operational challenges, this study intends to:

- **Identify** the specific elements of current law and policy that enable or constrain the use of National Guard personnel in Title 32 status for federal cyber missions.
- **Examine** historical precedents and expert analyses to determine how Title 32 authorities have been interpreted and applied in cybersecurity contexts.
- **Assess** the operational feasibility and strategic implications of leveraging Title 32 cyber forces for national security missions.
- **Provide** evidence-based recommendations for policymakers to enhance the clarity and effectiveness of Title 32 cyber force integration.

Central Proposition

National Guard Cyber Forces in Title 32 status can be used to support certain national defensive cyber missions, if a training requirement is met, **under existing law and policy.**

Message from Congress and Leaders

Message from Everyone Else

Why is this?

Authorities Landscape

The authority and responsibility for military operations conducted by the National Guard is derived from:

- United States Constitution
- Title 10 and Title 32 USC

U.S. Constitution Article I, Section 8, Clause 16:
[The Congress shall have Power . . .] To provide for organizing, arming, and disciplining, the Militia, and for governing such Part of them as may be employed in the Service of the United States, reserving to the States respectively, the Appointment of the Officers, and the Authority of training the Militia according to the discipline prescribed by Congress; . . .

Authorities Landscape

Provides **authority** and **responsibility** for actions conducted on behalf of government

U.S. Legal Authorities. (Joint Staff J7, 2013).

Authorities Landscape

US Code (USC)	Title	Key Focus	Principal Organization	Role in Cyberspace
Title 6	<i>Domestic Security</i>	Homeland Security	Department of Homeland Security (DHS)	Security of US cyberspace
Title 10	<i>Armed Forces</i>	National Defense	Department of Defense (DOD)	Man, train, and equip US forces for military operations in cyberspace
Title 32	<i>National Guard</i>	National defense and civil support training and operations, in the US	State Army National Guard (ARNG), State Air National Guard (ANG), National Guard Bureau (NGB)	Domestic consequence management (if activated for federal service, integrated into Title 10 USC, Armed Forces)
Title 50	<i>War and National Defense</i>	Military, foreign intelligence, and counterintelligence	Commands, Services, and agencies under DOD and Intelligence Community (IC) agencies aligned under the Director of National Intelligence (DNI)	Secure US interests by conducting military and foreign intelligence operations in cyberspace

Selected sections, U.S. Code. (Shankar, 2023)

Authorities Landscape

Oversight and activity breakdown (Oakley, 2019, p. 18)

Authorities Landscape

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Authorities Landscape

Oversight and activity breakdown (Oakley, 2019, p. 18)

Using NG Cyber Forces off-DoDIN

Positioning of figures is not absolute. There are exceptions. Size of figure indicates comparative level of use. Associated directives are mapped in later slides

Focus HDCMA
 NG Cyber Forces in T32 status, executing DCO in non-DoD-owned-cyberspace with DoD providing funding for the employment of those forces.

Legend

- T32 Title 32 Duty Status
- Serendipitous use of IDT/AT
- T32 § 502(f)(2). If ordered by POTUS, SECDEF
- T32 § 901-908, never used, future use in doubt
- SAD State Active Duty Status
- T10 Title 10 Duty Status

CTAA=Coordinate, Train, Advise and Assist
 DSCA=Defense Support to Civil Authorities
 DSCIR=Defense Support to Cyber Incident Response
 IRT=Innovative Readiness Training
 IDT/AT=Inactive Duty Training/Active Training
 IRA=Immediate Response Authority
 LFA=Lead Federal Agency
 METL=Mission Essential Task List
 PPD=Presidential Policy Directive

Authorities Landscape

PUBLIC LAW 114-328—DEC. 23, 2016

130 STAT. 2609

SEC. 1651. STRATEGY TO INCORPORATE ARMY RESERVE COMPONENT CYBER PROTECTION TEAMS INTO DEPARTMENT OF DEFENSE CYBER MISSION FORCE.

(a) **STRATEGY REQUIRED.**—Not later than 180 days after the date of the enactment of this Act, the Secretary of the Army shall provide to the Committees on Armed Services of the Senate and the House of Representatives a briefing on a strategy for incorporating reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense.

(b) **ELEMENTS OF STRATEGY.**—The strategy required by subsection (a) shall include, at minimum, the following:

(1) A timeline for incorporating reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense, including a timeline for the appropriate training of such teams.

(2) Identification of the specific reserve component cyber protection teams to be incorporated into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense.

(3) An assessment of how the incorporation of reserve component cyber protection teams into the cyber mission force of the Department of Defense might be used to enhance readiness through improved individual and collective training capabilities.

(4) A status report on the progress of the Army in issuing additional guidance that clarifies how reserve component cyber protection teams of the Army National Guard can support State and civil operations in National Guard status under title 32, United States Code.

(5) Other matters as considered appropriate by the Secretary of the Army.

(c) **RESERVE COMPONENT CYBER PROTECTION TEAMS DEFINED.**—In this section, the term “reserve component cyber protection teams” means cyber protection teams of—

(1) the Army National Guard; and

(2) the other reserve components of the Army.

Army National Guard Cyber Forces are still not being presented as part of the Cyber Mission Force (CMF).

The Army was directed by Congress to propose a strategy to do this in the FY17 NDAA, but it was not implemented.

This means questions about how this force can be utilized for cyber missions while in Title 32, or absent a specific federal mission, have not been answered.

Authorities Landscape

Utilization of National Guard and Reserve Forces in Cyberspace Operations

Over the last 10 years, Congress has expressed its position that the Department of Defense can bolster its operational capacity in cyberspace through improved utilization of the National Guard. This has resulted in 10 legislative provisions over a decade's worth of National Defense Authorization Acts and is most pertinently expressed through sections 1729 and 1730 of the William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021 (Public Law 116-283). Despite these calls for change, the Department of Defense and the military services appear not to have made any meaningful change in how the expertise resident within the National Guard and the Reserve Component can be better leveraged.

Therefore, the committee directs the Assistant Secretary of Defense for Cyber Policy, in coordination with the Commander, U.S. Cyber Command, to submit a report to the Senate Committee on Armed Services and the House Committee on Armed Services not later than May 31, 2024, on the specific actions and institutional obstacles that have prevented change from being instantiated after the requirements directed in the following legislative provisions:

(1) section 1651 of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2017 (Public Law 114-328);

(2) section 1653 of the John S. McCain National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2019 (Public Law 115-232); and

(3) section 1729 and 1730 of the William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021 (Public Law 116-283).

In the markup for the FY24 NDAA, Congress again directed DOD to explain why the cyber expertise in the National Guard is not being better utilized for operations.

Absent substantive, responsive action by DOD, the National Guard is still not being effectively utilized in support of operational cyber requirements while in Title 32.

Authorities Landscape

...and in the Senate version of the FY26 NDAA (not implemented):

SEC. 1605. REPORT ON RESERVE COMPONENT INTEGRATION INTO CYBER MISSION FORCE AND CYBERSPACE OPERATIONS.

(a) **REPORT REQUIRED.**—Not later than August 1, 2026, the Assistant Secretary of Defense for Cyber Policy and the Commander of United States Cyber Command shall jointly, in coordination with the Chief of the National Guard Bureau, the principal cyber advisors of each of the military departments, the chief of each reserve component, and the Office of the Under Secretary of Defense for Personnel and Readiness, submit to the congressional defense committees a report on the integration of the reserve components into the cyber mission force in support of cyberspace operations.

(b) **CONTENTS.**—The report required under subsection (a) shall include the following:

(1) An assessment of the different authorities available within each status of the reserve components, with particular focus on the National Guard and authorities under title 32, United States Code, and how the Department of Defense can use personnel of the reserve components in such statuses within the cyber mission force and in support of cyberspace operations.

(2) An analysis of current and planned efforts to work with the military departments, the National Guard, and the adjutants general of each State to develop unique cyber capabilities that address identified operational requirements and that maximize use of local industry expertise and academic partnerships.

(3) A description of methods to work with the military departments, the National Guard Bureau, and the adjutants general of each State to track and identify key skills and competencies that are not part of primary military occupational specialties of members of the military departments, but are developed through their civilian career experience.

(4) An identification of the billets, resources, and support infrastructure needed to maximize the unique expertise, capabilities, and authorities of the reserve components in support of the cyber mission of the Department.

(5) An evaluation of what types of authorities would be most beneficial to maximize the activation and support of the reserve components to cyberspace operations, including any legislative action that may be required.

Authorities Landscape

Final version of FY26 NDAA (Public Law 119-60)

Changes from 1605 to 1544:

Removal of requirements from ASW(Cyber), USW(P&R), Commander USCYBERCOM, CNGB, and Service PCAs

Removal of all references to National Guard, NGB, state Adjutants General, current and planned state programs

Removal of all references to authorities under Title 32

SEC. 1544. INTEGRATION OF RESERVE COMPONENT INTO CYBER MISSION FORCE.

(a) STUDY ON FORCE PRESENTATION, FORCE GENERATION, AND FORCE EMPLOYMENT OF THE RESERVE COMPONENT INTO THE CYBER MISSION FORCE.—

(1) STUDY REQUIRED.—Not later than October 1, 2026, the Secretary of Defense shall carry out a study on the appropriate framework for structuring and organizing, including training and preparing, the reserve component personnel and units to be employed within the Cyber Mission Force for cyberspace operations.

(2) ELEMENTS.—The study required under paragraph (1) shall include the following:

(A) An analysis of the types of cyberspace operations and missions of the Cyber Mission

Force that will maximize the use of the expertise, unique authorities, local industry expertise, and academic partnerships of reserve components, including methods to identify skills and competencies relevant to carrying out such operations and types of missions that are developed through civilian career experience and that are not part of primary military occupational specialties.

(B) An evaluation of optimal structures and organizations for integrating reserve component personnel and units into operational employment of cyber capabilities within the Cyber Mission Force, including consideration of operational models under which reserve component personnel are activated on an individual basis to perform cyber operations rather than activation on a unit basis.

Related Work and Literature Review

Limited work in this area

- Most are War College Theses and Military Policy Working Papers
- The topic of NG cyber force utilization started appearing around 2011
- Several examples of legislative language or markup referring to the issue

See references: Hollis, 2011; McKinney, 2013; Hopes, 2013; McCullouch, 2015; Claus et al., 2015; Kirschner & McGarry, 2015; Papenfus, 2016; Archer, 2016; Forscey & Ruiz, 2019; Muller & Thomas, 2020; Garcia, 2021; Neville, 2023; LaCroix, 2023; Kinch, 2023; Schroeder, 2023; FY 2014, 2017, 2019, 2021, 2022, 2024, 2026 NDAAs

Research gap

- Limited empirical studies on Title 32 cyber force integration
- Insufficient analysis of Title 32 cyber missions
- Lack of documented operational case studies

Federated Intelligence Program (FIP)

Department of Defense INSTRUCTION

NUMBER 3300.05

July 17, 2013

Incorporating Change 2, Effective August 7, 2020

USD(I&S)

SUBJECT: Reserve Component Intelligence Enterprise (RCIE) Management

Federated Intelligence Program (FIP)

Department of Defense INSTRUCTION

3. UNDER SECRETARY OF DEFENSE FOR PERSONNEL AND READINESS (USD(P&R)). The USD(P&R):

a. Develops Total Force policies that encourage RC recruiting and retention, achieve optimal alignment and integration of Active Component (AC) and RC personnel, facilitate efficient and effective training, and foster shared use of resources to provide the greatest operational benefit to missions pursuant to Reference (c) and in accordance with Vice Chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff and Assistant Secretary of Defense for Reserve Affairs Report (Reference (o)).

(1) Provide guidance and oversight for the development of programs that enable the operational capabilities of the RC as part of the Total Force.

(2) Develop policies to support the effective planning, organization, and use of the RC to provide operational support during inactive duty for training (IDT), annual training (AT), and active duty (AD) periods of service, including National Guard service pursuant to section 502 of Reference (f).

SUBJECT: Reserve Component Intelli

Federated Intelligence Program (FIP)

- “No MI Solider at rest” — “No Cold Starts”
 - Get service members *access, experience, and real-world work*
 - Fully integrate Reserve Component, including National Guard, into the Defense Intelligence Enterprise
 - ARNG participation in this effort is called FIP
- Support to Combatant Command (CCMD) or Intelligence Community (IC) Combat Support Agency (CSA)
- Soldiers in Title 32 status; Mission Manager for each support relationship may be in Title 10 status
- Soldiers gain experience, maintain proficiency, and have pride in the work they do on drill weekends

Can we do this for cyber?

(We need to...)

RC Support to AC and DOD Missions

Department of Defense **INSTRUCTION**

NUMBER 1215.06

March 11, 2014

Incorporating Change 2, July 12, 2022

USD(P&R)

SUBJECT: Uniform Reserve, Training, and Retirement Categories for the Reserve Components

RC Support to AC and DOD Missions

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SUBJECT: Uniform Reserve, Tr
Components

RC UTILIZATION CATEGORIES

1. GENERAL. The utilization categories provide the Secretaries of the Military Departments and the Commandant of the USCG the flexibility to develop policies to maximize RC utilization. In order to maximize RC utilization, all training duty planned and performed by RC Service members will capitalize on RC capabilities to accomplish operational requirements while maintaining their readiness for DoD missions. RC Service members may be employed to support AC mission requirements as part of conducting training duty. The appendix to this enclosure depicts the structure and relationships of RC utilization categories and duty types for ID, AD, and FTNGD under specific authorities. RC Service members may be utilized in one of the following four categories: training, support, mobilization, and other.

2. TRAINING. All RC Service members will receive training pursuant to assignments and required readiness levels. Required training will provide for the minimum training time or number of training periods required for attaining the prescribed unit readiness status and maintaining individual proficiency. The primary purpose of all training is the enhancement of individual skills and unit effectiveness. Mission support may be a key element in developing training programs, but training will be the paramount consideration and documented for budgetary allocations. DoD missions and OS may be accomplished incident to training. Required training parameters are further delineated in Enclosure 7.

RC Support to AC and DOD Missions

SUBJECT:

RC UTILIZATION CATEGORIES

Dep

1. GENERAL. The utilization categories provide the Secretaries of the Military Departments and the Commandant of the USCG the flexibility to develop policies to maximize RC utilization. In order to maximize RC utilization, all training duty planned and performed by RC Service members will capitalize on RC capabilities to accomplish operational requirements while maintaining their readiness for DoD missions. RC Service members may be employed to support AC mission requirements as part of conducting training duty. The appendix to this

a. Training may be conducted in an ID, AD, or FTNGD duty type. utilized in one of

b. The training utilization category consists of both voluntary and involuntary training duty. Involuntary training duty includes AT, IDT, and FTNGD-T (FTNGD-AT and FTNGD-OTD). Voluntary training duty includes ADT, IADT, OTD, and FTNGD-OTD.

c. Training may be conducted under the authority of 12301(b), 12301(d), and 10147 of Reference (d) or 502(f)(1)(A), 502(f)(1)(B), and 502(a) of Reference (f).

training programs, but training will be the paramount consideration and documented for budgetary allocations. DoD missions and OS may be accomplished incident to training. Required training parameters are further delineated in Enclosure 7.

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RC Support to AC and DOD Missions

32 U.S. Code § 502 - Required drills and field exercises

(a) Under regulations to be prescribed by the Secretary of the Army or the Secretary of the Air Force, as the case may be, each company, battery, squadron, and detachment of the National Guard, unless excused by the Secretary concerned, shall—

- (1) assemble for drill and instruction, including indoor target practice, at least 48 times each year; and
- (2) participate in training at encampments, maneuvers, outdoor target practice, or other exercises, at least 15 days each year.

(f)

(1) Under regulations to be prescribed by the Secretary of the Army or Secretary of the Air Force, as the case may be, a member of the National Guard may—

- (A) without his consent, but with the pay and allowances provided by law; or
- (B) with his consent, either with or without pay and allowances; be ordered to perform training or other duty in addition to that prescribed under subsection (a).

What's not here?

32 U.S. Code § 502 - Required drills and field exercises

(f)

(2) The training or duty ordered to be performed under paragraph (1) may include the following:

(A) Support of operations or missions undertaken by the member's unit at the request of the President or Secretary of Defense.

Why?

Because we know POTUS- or SECDEF-approved duty status under Title 32 502(f)(2)(A) supports certain cyber and other activities.

Bottom line: DoDI 1215.06 makes it clear that AC missions and DOD missions and operational support may occur "*incident to training*" under Title 32 § 502(a) (drills and AT), 501(f)(1)(A) (involuntary additional duty, with pay), and 501(f)(1)(B) (voluntary additional duty, with or without pay).

Training is paramount, but operational missions can be supported — including certain cyber missions.

So what's the problem?

It's not explicitly for cyber.

So what's the problem?

It's not explicitly for cyber.

It says "may" and not "shall".

So what's the problem?

It's not explicitly for cyber.

It says "may" and not "shall".

So the problem persists.

Problem Statement

The United States lacks a consistently understood and consistently executed legal–policy–operational pathway to use Title 32 authorities for national cyber mission support beyond training, resulting in underutilized cyber capacity, uneven governance, and inconsistent resourcing and approval processes.

The Gap

- ARNG Cyber Forces still not presented as part of CMF
- Congress directed strategy in FY17 NDAA — not implemented
- FY24 NDAA again asked why NG cyber not better utilized
- Debate has persisted for 15 years (since ~2011)

Why It Matters

- 4,000+ NG cyber operators across 40 states
- Many work in private sector tech/cyber roles
- Critical recruiting and retention challenge
- Fully training a 17C costs the Army \$400,000

What about Innovative Readiness Training (IRT)?

10 U.S. Code § 2012 - Support and services for eligible organizations and activities outside Department of Defense

[U.S. Code](#) [Notes](#)

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(a) AUTHORITY TO PROVIDE SERVICES AND SUPPORT.—Under regulations prescribed by the Secretary of Defense, the Secretary of a military department may in accordance with this section authorize units or individual members of the armed forces under that Secretary's jurisdiction to provide support and services to non-Department of Defense organizations and activities specified in subsection (e), but only if—

- (1)** such assistance is authorized by a provision of law (other than this section); or
- (2)** the provision of such assistance is incidental to military training.

DoD INSTRUCTION 1100.24

INNOVATIVE READINESS TRAINING (IRT): SUPPORT AND SERVICES FOR ELIGIBLE ORGANIZATIONS AND ACTIVITIES OUTSIDE DoD

What about Innovative Readiness Training (IRT)?

10 U.S. Code § 2012 - Support and services for eligible organizations and activities **outside Department of Defense**

U.S. Code Notes

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Fundamentally flows from Title 10 —
Title 32 IRT principles flow down

Focus is on support to organizations
and activities *outside* DoD

DoD INSTRUCTION 1100.24

INNOVATIVE READINESS TRAINING (IRT): SUPPORT AND
SERVICES FOR ELIGIBLE ORGANIZATIONS AND ACTIVITIES
OUTSIDE DoD

What about Innovative Readiness Training (IRT)?

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Department of

U.S. Code Notes

(a) AUTHORITY TO PROVIDE SERVICE
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 but only if—

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- (2)** the provision of such

Fundamentally flows from Title 10 —
 Title 32 IRT principles flow down

Our focus is on support to AC missions or DOD missions and operational support, incident to training, within DOD components (e.g., CYBERCOM, NSA), using cyber personnel in cyber units for defensive cyber functions.

rt to organizations
 de DoD

INNOVATIVE READINESS TRAINING (IRT): SUPPORT AND SERVICES FOR ELIGIBLE ORGANIZATIONS AND ACTIVITIES

OUTSIDE DoD

The Core Problem

Despite senior leaders repeatedly stating that National Guard cyber forces are essential to national cyber defense, they are not systematically integrated into national cyber missions under Title 32.

Legal, policy, and bureaucratic ambiguities and service cultures prevent full utilization, even though existing policy and precedent suggests current viable pathways for involvement.

CO and the CMF

Cyberspace Operations Missions, Actions, and Forces

Legend

- CCMD combatant command
- CMT combat mission team
- CPT cyberspace protection team
- DODIN Department of Defense information network
- NMT national mission team

Department of Defense Cyber Mission Force Relationships

Legend

- CCMD combatant command
- CPT cyberspace protection team
- DODIN Department of Defense information network

Command and Control in the CMF

Routine Cyberspace Command and Control

* CO-IPE is provided by USCYBERCOM in direct support of combatant commander. Organizational relationships between CO-IPEs and USCYBERCOM subordinate headquarters will be specified via USCYBERCOM orders.

Legend

CCMD	combatant command	JFHQ-C	joint force headquarters-cyberspace
CMT	combat mission team	JFHQ-DODIN	Joint Force Headquarters-Department of Defense Information Network
CNMF-HQ	Cyber National Mission Force Headquarters	NMT	national mission team
COCOM	combatant command (command authority)	NST	national support team
CO-IPE	cyberspace operations-integrated planning element	OPCON	operational control
CPT	cyberspace protection team	TACON	tactical control
CST	combat support team	USCYBERCOM	United States Cyber Command
DACO	directive authority for cyberspace operations		
DOD	Department of Defense		
DODIN	Department of Defense information network		
JCC	Joint Cyber Center		

	COCOM
	OPCON
	TACON
	DACO
	supporting/supported
	direct support
	coordination

Types of NG Cyber Units

Army National Guard

Cyber Protection Teams

Defend the DODIN, protect priority missions, prepare forces for combat

Defensive Cyber Ops Elements

Defensive internal measures to secure National Guard portion of the DODIN & respond to state cyber emergencies as directed by Governor or Adjutant General

Cyber Warfare Companies

Full spectrum cyber operations support, OPFOR support to exercises, & pen-testing

Cyber Security Companies

Vulnerability assessments, forensics analysis, Industrial Control Systems expertise, USCYBERCOM Readiness Inspections, cybersecurity support

Air National Guard

Cyber Protection Teams

Defend the DODIN, protect priority missions, prepare force for combat

Mission Defense Teams

Defensive cyber operations on specific weapons platform/system

National Mission Teams

Intelligence-driven cyber operations against nation state actors in defense of the nation

Red Team

Vulnerability assessments of friendly networks in support of Combatant Command & Service requirements

What can the NG do for national missions while in Title 32? Proposition, restated:

- Perform cyber *protective/defensive* function
 - Defensive Cyberspace Operations (DCO)
 - DCO–Internal Defensive Measures (DCO-IDM)
 - Cyberspace Defense
 - DODIN Operations
 - Cyberspace Security
- Consistent with policy and precedent to date
- People intuitively understand that Cyber **Protection** Teams perform a defensive (Cyberspace Defense or Cyberspace Security) function
- Outside of the scope of this research:
 - Other Cyberspace Operations that “reach out”: OCO, DCO-RA (Cyberspace Attack)

Utilization Exemplar

Training
Requirements
(METL)

Title 32
Support

Mission
Requirements
(Operational)

Where do we need to be for Title 32?

DODIN Ops

Cyberspace Action

Title 10
(AD only)

Title 32 (any)

SAD

Cyberspace Security (*Network Defense*) Cyberspace security actions are taken within protected cyberspace...threat-informed, cyberspace security actions occur in advance of a specific security compromise and are a primary component action of the DODIN operations mission.

Training (OR operations when authorized by POTUS or SECWAR)

As directed by State Governor

DCO-IDM

Cyberspace Defense (*Network Defense*) Cyberspace defense actions are taken within protected cyberspace to defeat specific threats that have breached or are threatening to breach the cyberspace security measures and include actions to detect, characterize, counter, and mitigate threats, including malware or the unauthorized activities of users, and to restore the system to a secure configuration.

Training (OR operations when authorized by POTUS or SECWAR)

As directed by State Governor

DCO-RA

Cyberspace Exploitation (*Cyber Collection/Cyber Effects Enabling Activities*) Cyberspace exploitation actions include military intelligence activities, maneuver, information collection, and other enabling actions required to prepare for future military operations.

Training (OR operations when authorized by POTUS or SECWAR)

OCO

Cyberspace Attack (*Cyber Effect*) Cyberspace attack actions create noticeable denial effects (i.e., degradation, disruption, or destruction) in cyberspace or manipulation that leads to denial effects in the physical domains.

Only when authorized

How do we address the problem?

- National Guard personnel are in Title 32 status for:
 - Drill (e.g., weekend training) — 502(a)
 - Training (Annual Training, other) — 502(a), other
 - Operational Support — 502(f)(1) and (2)
- Title 32 duty status supports *training* for federal mission
- Need to find training tasks which *also* fulfill mission requirement
 - *Primary* priority is training
 - *Secondary* benefit is mission support
- Complicated authorities and policy landscape

Identify use cases that support training *and* federal missions.

How do we find solutions?

- **Law and Policy**
 - Identify *existing* relevant law and policy
- **Expert Opinion**
 - Find examples of established precedent
 - Consensus among subject matter experts
 - Document experiences in this area
- **Give NG units and leaders confidence to implement**

Because this area is not well-established or well-understood by many policymakers or the general population, we need to bring together a combination of supporting policy, precedent, and expert views.

Research Design

Multi-Method Qualitative Research

Adapted DSRM

Research Goal

Why conduct this research?

The results of the research will develop a better understanding of the ability to utilize National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 Status for national cyber missions, in order to enable:

- **Recruiting and retention of military cyber experts in the reserve force**
 - Engage personnel in meaningful work while meeting training requirements
- **Meet clearly stated goals and intent for utilization of Guard Cyber**
 - Engage the Guard effectively aligned with national cyber mission needs

Documentary Analysis

Document Sources

- Unites States Constitution
- United States Code (USC)
 - Title 10 USC — Armed Forces
 - Title 32 USC — National Guard
 - Title 50 USC — War and National Defense
- DOD Policy, Directives, Instructions, and Memoranda
 - Department wide policy (DOD Instructions, Directives, and Memoranda)
 - Combatant Command (CCMD) or Combat Support Agency (CSA) policy
 - US Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM) Cyber Warfare Publications (CWP)
 - National Security Agency (NSA) cyber publications
 - Service policy (Army and Air Force policy)
 - Army Cyber Command (ARCYBER) publications
 - Air Forces Cyber (AFCYBER) publications
 - National Guard Bureau (NGB) policy
- Other Government publications
- Academic journals
- News articles
- Military school theses and papers
- Published reports

With the exceptions of the U.S. Constitution and U.S. Code, document searches are scoped to publication since the year 2000.

Documentary Analysis

Source	Key Focus	Coding
U.S. Constitution Art. I, §8, Cl. 16	Militia organizing, arming, disciplining; state training authority	Enabling
32 USC §502(a) and (f)	Required drills, field exercises; additional duty with/without pay	Enabling
DoDI 1215.06	RC utilization categories; mission support incident to training	Enabling
DoDI 3300.05 (FIP)	Federated Intelligence Program; RC integration precedent	Enabling
DoDI 3025.18 DoDI 3025.22 (DSCA)	Define procedures for cyber incident response	Enabling Procedural
AR 350–1 & NGR 350–1	Codifies operational support with “training first” strategy	Enabling
Domestic Ops Law Handbook	Legal basis for NG operational support in Title 32 status	Enabling
JP 3-12, USCYBERCOM CWP	Cyberspace operations doctrine; CMF training/readiness	Conditional
32 USC §502(f)(2)(A)	POTUS/SECDEF-approved operational support	Conditional

See dissertation for full analysis

Documentary Analysis

~80%

of documents coded
as Enabling

~20%

Conditional/
Ambiguous

0%

Strictly
Prohibitive

Key Finding

32 USC §502, DoDI 1215.06, DoDI 3300.05, and the 2024 Domestic Operational Law Handbook collectively establish a legal pathway in which training-aligned operational support under Title 32 can contribute to federal cyber missions. No documents were coded as strictly prohibitive.

Existing law and policy already provide sufficient authority to integrate National Guard cyber forces into national missions (AC missions or OS) when structured as training-based operational or mission support.

Surveys

Survey Participants

Current or former military, civilian, industry, and academic participants familiar with both the National Guard (Army or Air) and United States military cyber operations in a policy or legal context, at the national and state levels.

Participants are in a cyber or cyber-related field, or in a policy or legal field relevant to cyber operations, or familiar with the policy or legal landscape.

Use freeform and structured survey questions to collect information on:

- Existing precedent
- Expert opinions and analysis
- Experiences

Survey Demographics

151

Total Respondents

60

Complete Responses

86.7%

Worked with NG
Cyber Personnel

53.4%

10+ Years Cyber
Experience

Years in Cyber Operations (Q2)

Band	Count	%
No experience	2	3.3%
< 5 years	11	18.3%
5–10 years	15	25.0%
11–15 years	12	20.0%
16–20 years	7	11.7%
> 20 years	13	21.7%

NG Status Distribution (Q1.1)

- Actively Drilling (M-Day): 53.5%
- Retired: 14.0%
- FTNGD/ADOS/AGR: 7.0%
- Separated: 7.0%
- Active Duty — Title 10: 7.0%
- Other (AD-T32, Tech, SAD): 11.7%

Survey Findings – RQ1: Law & Policy

Q7.1: Law/policy
enable support (general)

4.07

mean (1–5)

79.7% agree

Q7.2: Law/policy
enable support (cyber)

3.90

mean (1–5)

71.2% agree

Q8: Legal/policy
barriers exist

3.49

mean (1–5)

57.6% agree

Precedent Awareness (Q9)

54.2% aware of existing precedent for Title 32 cyber support to national objectives

45.8% unaware — yet support was consistent across both groups

Interpretation

Respondents largely agree existing authorities can enable support, while also recognizing policy friction — the barrier is implementation clarity, not statutory absence.

Survey Findings – RQ2: Feasible Missions (Q10)

Strongest consensus: DCO-IDM and DoDIN Ops (86.2% each); more mixed for offensive actions

Survey Findings – RQ2: Key Indicators

84.7%

Q11: T32 can meet training
AND national mission
(Agree/SA)

66.7%

Q13: Federated support
can scale effectively
(Yes)

5.67

Q18: Confidence current
law supports missions
(Mean 0–10)

7.90

Q19: Benefit of structured
national program
(Mean 0–10)

Legislative Clarification (Q20, N=60)

■ Yes — support NDA language ■ It depends ■ No changes required ■ No

Funding & Governance (Q21–Q23)

Funding importance (0–10):

- Full-time orders: 7.69
- Ad hoc orders: 7.64
- Specialized training: 7.73
- Manager on full-time orders: 7.12
- Manager in Title 10 status: 5.30

Funding entity preferences:

- Customer (CCMD/CSA): 74.1%
- NGB: 56.9%
- Service Cyber Component: 51.7%

Survey Findings – Themes

Five Major Themes from Qualitative Analysis

Survey Findings – Top Subthemes

Dominant pattern: policy gaps and need for national–state coordination, not legal prohibitions

Survey Findings – Practitioner Views

Dominant View: Policy Gaps, Not Legal Prohibitions

“Legal or policy barriers don’t exist, it’s just that the landscape is confusing, and there are certainly organizational barriers and risk aversion.”

— ARNG Officer, 20+ years cyber

“The barriers are procedural and knowledge-based, not legal. [...] many leaders and planners do not fully understand how to properly employ National Guard cyber assets.”

— ARNG Enlisted, 16–20 years

Contrary View: Real Barriers Exist

“The status of the orders hinders members from actively participating in some mission sets. It was all because I went under [Title] 32 instead of [Title] 10 orders.”

— ANG, 5–10 years

“I was a GS 14 Tech Director in Special Operations and I was sent to learn basic networking as an E5. I basically paid \$30k to go to school for something I was an expert in.”

— ANG, 5–10 years

This disagreement is itself a finding: practitioners inhabit a landscape of genuine interpretive uncertainty.

Case Study

- Conduct pilot program with the Wisconsin Army National Guard's Detachment 1 176th Cyber Protection Team (Det 1-176 CPT)
- Det 1-176 CPT was mobilized on Task Force Echo (TFE) from Nov 2020 to Jan 2022 conducting cyberspace operations in support of US Cyber Command and Cyber National Mission Force (CNMF)
- After the mobilization, we looked for ways to continue to engage members of the CPT in meaningful work while maintaining mission proficiency
- Met with partner and agreed to establish pilot program
- Wisconsin Federated Cyber Program (WIFCP) was born (Dec 2021)
- Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) signed (Nov 2022)

Case Study — WIFCP

- Provide support to Intelligence Community (IC) partner
- Cybersecurity research and situational awareness
 - *Not* an intelligence or intelligence-related activity
- Briefed to IC Agency Director; Army G2; ARNG G2; NGB J2 IO; NGB IG; State JAG, IG
- MOA directly between IC component and WING
- Covers any MOS/AOC/AFSC and unit in Title 32 and Title 10

Case Study — WIFCP

- Use Cyber personnel (17 Series)
- Use Cyber units (e.g., CPT, DCOE, CRT)
- *Perform tasks:*
 - Consistent with Defensive Cyberspace Operations (DCO) or DODIN Operations *and* which conform with:
 - USCYBERCOM CWP 3-2 (DCO), CWP 3-33.4 (CPT), CTM 7-0.2: Cyber Mission Force (CMF) Training and Readiness (T&R)
 - ARCYBER DCO FY23-28 DCO Training Objectives
- *...that also:*
 - Meet a customer mission requirement

Case Study — WIFCP

- Soldiers volunteer for WIFCP
- Monitor cyber and related news for a particular area of operation (AOR) of interest from public media and cybersecurity research sources
- Compile weekly Cyber News Summary
- Deliver to unclassified (U) and classified (TS) networks
 - Email, Intelink IntelDocs, ChatSurfer
- Fills an information gap for mission partners focused on classified reporting, or without routine access to suitable unclassified or non-attributable research tools in their work environments

Case Study — WIFCP

- Operates in the context of MOA between IC agency and Wisconsin National Guard
- Explicitly acknowledges operation in Title 32 status and the use of cybersecurity (CS) context
- Uses cyber personnel in a cyber role performing cyber function (i.e., not intelligence or intelligence-related activity)
 - Reduces complexity and increases effectiveness
 - *This is the key to our program*

Case Study — By the Numbers

For the period 1 January 2025 to 30 April 2025:

- 4 Det 1-176 CPT Soldiers
- 2 Officer, 2 Enlisted

- Title 32 duty status
- Paid and retirement points

- 152 hours (total)
- 38 hours/Soldier (avg)

- 17 Cyber News Summaries
- Associated Weekly Reports

- >200 recipients across DOD and IC relevant to this AOR
- 1,670 news articles
 - 207 cyber related (12%)
- 152 cyber reports from other sources
 - 62 additional products from the CrowdStrike Falcon platform provided via Army Cyber Command (ARCYBER) to augment cybersecurity reporting

Case Study — Results

- Positive comments from DOD and IC mission customers

“Much appreciate these weekly reports! They are always well received here!”

“I really appreciate the diversity of articles and the general lack of redundancy among other press reports we get via other reporting repositories.”

“Thank you for the continued reporting, it’s super helpful to USCYBERCOM J2 when trying to track all the [...] cyber activity and briefing our leadership.”

“Just wanted to thank you for the work you do. We really value your summaries!”

“Appreciate the work that you do!”

“This is on par if not better than the stuff we get through serialized reporting. It is mind boggling as to who is sharing this stuff and that it is available in open source.”

“Thank you for doing these. I am amazed at the stuff that is just out there in open source every time I look at what you have sent out.”

“We have been tasked with providing a weekly cyber “roll-up” to our cyber defensive network team. Your summary is really handy for that!”

“Your summaries and reports are invaluable to [our] team in order to find out more of the technical details and expert analysis from those industry partners that we would not normally have access to. So thank you for your efforts and anytime you'd like to talk [...] cyber we are available.”

“I look forward to your emails and have come to rely on them. I always direct my team of analysts to read this email and apply the info to the all source analysis we are doing here. Do you intend to continue to do this type of product? I hope so!”

Case Study — Results: \$800K impact

- Positive retention results for Soldiers
 - Two Enlisted Soldiers selected to work on this program stated that they decided to re-enlist at the end of their service obligation because of the ability to work on a program providing real world mission support; one just completed WOAC and is now a WO1!
- Critical outcome of this program!
 - Training a 17C costs the Army \$400,000
 - We need to utilize and *retain* these Soldiers!

Case Study — Needs

- **Ways to allocate Soldiers to missions**
- **Mechanism to allocate funding to periodic Title 32 orders (MIPR from agency to NGB to State to unit)**
 - **Only mechanism for compensated support can't be long-term Title 10 orders**
 - **This is the whole problem with Guard and Reserve support: treated only as active-duty surge / “plug-in”**
- **Program needs buy-in and support from State leadership and mission partner**

Case Study — End State

- Mission support while in Title 32
- Continuity with federal mobilization — people, missions, AORs
- Deliver a more integrated force to support national missions

Case Study — More Information

For more information on this pilot at the Controlled Unclassified Information (CUI) or TOP SECRET (TS) levels, users with appropriate access may visit:

- **Intelink-U:** <https://go.intelink.gov/WIFCP>
- **Intelink-TS (JWICS):** <https://go.ic.gov/WIFCP>

Expected Policy Implications

- **Clarify Title 32 Cyber Authorities** – Establish clear understanding regarding Guard cyber force utilization for national missions.
- **Create a National Guard Cyber Integration Strategy** – Define a formalized framework for aligning Guard cyber personnel with DoD cyber operations.
- **Enhance Understanding of Title 32–Title 10 Interoperability** – Improve coordination and training pathways between Guard cyber units and federal cyber teams.
- **Give NG units and leaders confidence to implement** – Leaders and staff on both ends of prospective support relationships are unsure how to proceed, and too often the answer is to do nothing.

What's next?

The National Guard's Title 32 authorities enable unique options for support to national cyber needs.

The key is meeting documented training requirements for Title 10 cyber missions under existing fiscal and mission authorities.

Core Findings and Themes

- 1 Existing authorities are more enabling than commonly assumed.
- 2 Practitioners view Title 32 as feasible for specific mission types, but not without governance fixes.
- 3 The dominant barriers are implementation ambiguity and institutional friction, not categorical legal prohibitions.
- 4 WIFCP demonstrates a workable Title 32 mission-support model and highlights force-management value.

Key Recommendations

Organizational and Structural

Clarify and institutionalize roles and relationships for Title 32 cyber support:

- Designate clear points of responsibility within U.S. Cyber Command and the National Guard Bureau for Title 32 cyber integration.
- Formalize mission manager roles for federated cyber programs (analogous to federated mission management constructs used elsewhere).
- Encourage state-level cyber integration working groups (TAG, state J-staff, key unit leaders) to align state and federal priorities.

Key Recommendations

Governance and Implementation

Treat Title 32 cyber utilization as a cybersecurity risk governance problem and operationalize it with repeatable processes

- Develop a formal **Title 32 Cyber Integration Profile** that specifies mission categories appropriate for Title 32 support (e.g., DCO–IDM, DoDIN Ops, cybersecurity situational awareness) and the conditions/expected outcomes.
- Establishing standardized request/approval artifacts (templates for training alignment, legal review, and oversight).
- Creating standardized metrics and reporting (e.g., number of federated programs, training hours logged on mission, mission impact assessments) to enable oversight and congressional visibility.

Key Recommendations

Strategic Alignment and Policy Development

Explicitly align Title 32 cyber integration to national strategy and doctrine:

- Develop a **National Guard Cyber Integration Strategy** describing how Title 32 supports national objectives, how it relates to the Cyber Mission Force, and how it contributes to broader multi-domain posture.
- Use FY26 NDAA-directed RC CMF integration imperative as a roadmap for assessing authorities, leveraging civilian-acquired skills, and identifying billets/infrastructure and barriers.
- Incorporate lessons from pilots like WIFCP into joint/service doctrine/policy so federated Title 32 models become recognized options — like FIP — rather than one-off experiments.

Results Published Online

A white silhouette of a Minuteman soldier from the American Revolutionary War, wearing a tricorn hat and holding a long rifle. The figure is positioned on the left side of a dark blue rectangular area.

TITLE 32 CYBER SURVEY

T32Cyber.org

Survey Data Explorer

UNCLASSIFIED // DAKOTA STATE UNIVERSITY DOCTORAL RESEARCH

Dark

Title 32 Cyber Survey Results

Utilization of National Guard Cyber Forces in Title 32 Status for National Cyber Missions

TOTAL RESPONSES

151

COMPLETE

60

SURVEY PERIOD

Jun-Oct 2025

COMPLETION RATE

40%

DATA FILTER:

Complete Only

Overview

Demographics

Law & Policy

Operations

Integration

Funding & Admin

Open Responses

Analysis

Filters

// Executive Summary

KEY FINDINGS

Strong Support for Title 32 Enablement

80% of respondents agree that current law/policy enables Title 32 support to national missions.

Training-Mission Alignment

85% agree that Title 32 activities can be structured to meet training requirements and contribute to national mission objectives.

High Benefit Perception

Mean rating of 7.9/10 for benefit of a structured national program to align NG cyber with national needs.

Q18 VS Q19 (N_{COMPLETE} = 58)

OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

Confidence that Title 32 can support national missions (Q18) vs. Perceived benefit of a structured national program (Q19)

● Respondents ● Regression ($R^2 = 0.179$)

Q7.1 (N_{COMPLETE} = 59)

LEGAL & POLICY

Current federal law and policy allow for the use of National Guard personnel to support Active Component (AC) missions or operational support (OS) of national missions while in Title 32 status.

Conclusion

The United States does not primarily face an authorities gap for employing National Guard cyber forces in Title 32 status for certain defensive national cyber missions; it faces a governance and execution gap.

Documentary evidence, practitioner consensus, and the federated cyber program operational proof-of-concept converge on the same implication:

A deliberate, structured Title 32 cyber integration approach is both feasible and necessary to scale Guard cyber capacity for national missions while preserving the training-first requirement and sustaining the force through meaningful work and retention benefits.

Contributions and Future Research

Contributions

- Integrated legal–policy–operational synthesis across documentary, survey, and case data
- Clarification of training–mission boundary in cyberspace
- Operationalization of a federated cyber support model (WIFCP)
- Empirical insight into practitioner perspectives (first survey of this expert community)
- Policy-relevant knowledge for cyber force development

Future Research

- Comparative state-level studies of NG cyber programs
- WIFCP replication across states with varying conditions
- Quantitative readiness & retention evaluation
- Boundary conditions for DCO-RA and OCO
- Governance frameworks tailored to Title 32 cyber (NIST CSF profiles)
- Integration with emerging force designs (CYBERCOM 2.0, potential Cyber Force)

Limitations: Unclassified sources only; non-probability expert sample; single-state case study; dynamic policy environment. 39.7% survey completion rate, though consistent across demographic subgroups.

With 4,000 National Guard cyber operators across 40 states, many working for leading tech companies, the National Guard has the knowledge, skills, and abilities to play a critical role in the DoD's cyber enterprise.

GEN Daniel Hokanson

Former Chief, National Guard Bureau

Q&A

Questions?

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